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Hyderabad

In Collaboration with

INDIAN DISTANCE EDUCATION ASSOCIATION

Organising

3 Day International Conference

on

**“DISSEMINATING LEARNING, DIMINISHING BORDERS
- ODL IN 21st CENTURY”**

(April 5th -7th, 2013)

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Availability of Internet Resources and Services for Open and Distance Learners (ODL): A Study of IGNOU & Dr. BRAOU

Dr. Mothukuri Anjaiah *

This paper mainly focused on to provide the Internet resources and e-services for distance learners as desired by them. This is a case study of IGNOU and Dr.BRAOU study centers from Warangal district i.e. Lal Bahadur College, Warangal and Arts & Science College, Warangal. For this study, 450 respondents were taken into consideration as sample. Data collected from the respondents randomly from all the disciplines.

A large majority of respondents (95%) demanding that Internet resources such as e-books, e-Journals, e-databases, e-theses, e-Information and e- Services like- E-Mail, SMS Alert Service, Book Marking Service, Ask Librarian, Using Social Networks , Mobile Services ,CAS, SDI Services, Bibliographical Services etc. and 24x7 Help Line Services should be provided at their desk top. 85% of the respondents demanding that every study center should have a Internet Lab with sufficient number of computer terminals with UPS facility. It is a good sign from the respondents. This study shows that the time has come to satisfy the distance learners as per their requirements by the premier institutions in India. The western education system i.e.UK, USA and other countries are providing e-resources and e-services at their desk top 24x7 .Hence, this study found that the all the Open and Distance Education Institutions should be change in their polices and programmes towards the distance learners in India to provide ICT/WEB facilities as well as services.

Keywords: Internet, E-Resources, E-services, Alert Services, Ask Librarian Service

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User Friendly ICTs for Teacher Training Programmes in Urdu Medium Through Distance Learning

Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel*, Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari**

The information communication technology (ICT) is playing vital role in present era dominated by technological innovations. The use of ICT is continuously increasing and the use of ICT involves dynamic processes including various concepts, methods, applications. Hence, there is no proper definition of ICT, but for simple understanding the three terms information, communication and technology guide us to make us understand ICT. Precisely this is use of technology for communicating the content and information to the intended communicatee or student. Thus, ICTs are a "diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate, and to create, disseminate, store, and manage information." The ICTs have been exploited to larger extent by the learners in distance education, as lot of information is being transferred to the learner through use of innovative technologies. There are a large number of technologies listed under ICT. The technologies like radio, television, internet, MS Office, educational blogs, online encyclopedias (like Wikipedia), social networking sites (like